

CHALKONES. PART III. SYNTHESIS OF METHYLCHALKONES

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Eight new chalkones have been synthesised by the Claisen-Schmidt condensation and their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones have been prepared.

In continuation of the previous work (Dhar and Lal, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, **23**, 1159) on chalkones, the present paper records the synthesis of some hitherto-unknown chalkones with different substituents, viz., methyl, methoxy, hydroxy, present either in the styryl or in the phenyl nucleus.

**EXPERIMENTAL

Resacetophenone dimethyl ether (Perkin *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, **93**, 1109), *o*-tolylaldehyde (Williams *et al.*, "Org. Syntheses," Coll. Vol. III, 1955, p. 349), and *p*-tolylaldehyde (Coleman and Craig, "Org. Syntheses", Coll. Vol. II, 1943, p. 583) were prepared as described previously. *m*-Tolylaldehyde was prepared from *m*-tolunitrile *via* Stephen's reaction (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1874).

2 : 4-Dimethylacetophenone was prepared in 54% yield by a slight modification of the method of Perkin and Stone (*ibid.*, 1925, 2283), using aluminium chloride instead of anhydrous ferric chloride. Its 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from ethyl acetate in deep orange-red microneedles, m.p. 170-70.5°. (Found : N, 16.91. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{18}O_4N_4$: N, 17.07%).

When wetted with concentrated sulphuric acid the chalkones, described herein, exhibit halochromism—the colour imparted range from orange to deep red. Ferric chloride develops a light brown colour with an ethanolic solution of 2-hydroxy-2' : 5'-dimethylchalkone, while the isomeric 2-hydroxy-2' : 4'-dimethylchalkone (I) fails to respond to this test. Furthermore, it is interesting to find that (I) melts to a green liquid, which dissolves in benzene with the production of a violet colour, while the crystalline chalkone, in benzene, forms a pale yellow solution.

2 : 5-Dimethylacetophenone was prepared by the Friedel-Crafts reaction of *p*-xylene with acetyl chloride by the method described by Fleisher and Freund (*Annalen*, 1917, **414**, 5). The 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from ethyl acetate in elongated biconvex plates, m.p. 170-71°, depressed to 150° on admixture with the isomeric 2 : 4-dimethylacetophenone 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (m.p. 170-70.5°). (Found : N, 17.05. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{18}O_4N_4$: N, 17.07%).

The synthesis of chalkones was effected according to the procedure of Schraufstätter and Deutsch (*Chem. Ber.*, 1948, **81**, 489). The method consists in the addition of about 50% aqueous KOH to benzaldehyde and acetophenone derivative in ethanol and keeping the mixture at room temperature for several hours as such or heating for a short time on a water-bath. The various chalkones prepared are recorded in Table I and their corresponding 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazones in Table II.

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** All melting points are uncorrected.

TABLE I

Chalkone.	Colour & cryst. shape.	Crystallised from.	M.P.	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
2':4'-Dimethoxy-4-methyl-	Bright yellow tiny prismatic needles	Ethanol	117°	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₂	76.50	76.63	6.50	6.40
2'-Hydroxy-2-methyl-	Yellow rhombic crystals	..	83-84°	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₂	80.69	80.67	5.81	5.88
2'-Hydroxy-3-methyl-	Yellow silky needles	..	64°	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₂	80.81	80.67	5.62	5.88
2'-Hydroxy-4-methyl-	Yellow rectangular plates	..	117-18°	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₂	80.54	80.67	6.11	5.88
2-Hydroxy-2':5'-dimethyl-	Yellow clusters of biconvex microplates	Aq. ethanol	120-21	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂	80.72	80.95	6.30	6.34
4-Methoxy-2':5'-dimethyl-	Yellow rectangular plates	Ethanol	85-85.5°	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₂	80.92	81.20	6.54	6.76
2-Hydroxy-2':4'-dimethyl-	Yellow microneedles	Aq. ethanol	115°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂	80.58	80.95	6.25	6.34
4-Methoxy-2':4'-dimethyl-	Pale yellow rectangular crystals	Ethanol	40-41°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂	81.43	81.20	6.57	6.76

TABLE II

Chalkone 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone.	Colour & cryst. shape.	Crystallised from.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.
2'-Hydroxy-2-methyl-	Vermilion-coloured long needles	Xylene	224-25°	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄	13.26	13.39
2'-Hydroxy-3-methyl-	Vermilion-coloured clusters of radiating needles	..	222-23°	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄	13.50	13.39
2'-Hydroxy-4-methyl-	Bright red flat microneedles	..	237°	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄	13.42	13.39
2-Hydroxy-2':5'-dimethyl-	Vermilion-coloured hexagonal crystals	Ethanol-ethyl acetate	233-35°	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₄	12.64	12.96
4-Methoxy-2':5'-dimethyl-	Red flat microneedles	Ethyl acetate	181-82°	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₄	12.85	12.55
2-Hydroxy-2':4'-dimethyl-	Vermilion-coloured microneedles	..	239-40°	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₄	12.54	12.96
4-Methoxy-2':4'-dimethyl-	Bright red microneedles	Xylene	218°	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₄	12.38	12.55

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